

THE ROLE OF STATUS ART IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH**Rozimatov Asrorbek**

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Abstract. This article describes the history of the development of status art, the work of our ancestors who contributed to status art, the role and importance of this art form, which is considered our national value, in the development of young people, the development of our national art, and the elimination of shortcomings in this field. done

Key words: status art, shashmaqom, value, national feeling, spiritual maturity.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated November 17, 2017 "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status" was signed. Currently, in our country, the Maqom ensemble named after Yunus Rajabi, Maqom ensembles in the regions, a special department in this direction at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan is operating, and scientific research is being conducted in this field. Also, teaching our national art, folk oral creativity, teaching the secrets of status in the national singing education department of the Faculty of Folklore, established at the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan. placed

The art of national status, which is an integral part of the cultural heritage of our people, occupies an important place in our spiritual life with its ancient history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style and rich creative traditions.

Over the centuries, this unique art, which has been polished by the hard work and dedication and creative thinking of great poets and scientists, skilled composers, hafiz and musicians, has gained great fame and attention not only in our country and eastern countries, but also on a global scale.

The fact that "Shashmaqom" is recognized as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity by UNESCO and included in its representative list is a clear confirmation of this. It is worth noting that it is necessary to increase the understanding of young people about the art of status, to widely promote our national cultural heritage, to preserve and convey it in its original state for our future generations. It is necessary to train personnel for music schools in remote areas of our

republic, increase the interest of our youth in the art of status and improve the quality of education.

It is necessary to teach music more deeply in secondary special education schools in remote areas of our country, we should teach music from the 1st grade in schools in remote villages of our country, and give more in-depth education about our national art to senior classes in the music textbook, national "Shashmaqom" "We need to increase the understanding of the series, to start teaching national musical instruments, and also to increase the monthly salary of our teachers who teach music in schools. We need to increase the number of lessons in music in our schools. If we launch these important initiatives, the increase in the interest of our youth in music will serve as an important foundation for introducing the rise of our national art to the world.

The musical culture of the Uzbek people has a centuries-old history. Many generations of musicians and singers have been active since ancient times. This is evidenced by the mastery of music in folk traditions. Ancient music culture of Central Asia In the territory of Uzbekistan there was an ancient civilization created by the ancestors of the peoples of Central Asia.

The stage of historical limitation in the life of the peoples of Central Asia began approximately several thousand years ago. These were settled farmers (Sugdians, Bactrians, Khorezimi) and nomadic tribes (Saks, Massagets, and others). Information about them can be found in "Avesta". The book "Avesta" and other ancient written monuments provide information about the fact that folk poetic and musical art was initially in a syncretic state.

The art of music has been considered an integral part of the culture of the peoples living in the territories of Central Asia since ancient times. Its directions, genres, forms were formed and developed in Central Asia, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iran and Eastern Turkestan, the ancestors of the Uzbek people, and the steppes and forests of the vast region stretching from the northern borders of China to Europe. began to develop in peoples who lived in mountainous regions. The improvement of the art of music is connected with the development of the cultural life of cities, and its roots go back to the end of the second millennium BC and the first millennium BC. Yunis Rajabi, the great figures of our art who contributed to the development of Uzbek music and the preservation of our national heritage to the next generations without defects. known as a talented singer and a skilled musician. His titles are People's Artist of Uzbekistan, Academician of the Academy of Sciences, excerpts from his repertoire, "Girya", "Ushoq", "Kucha Bogi", "Eshvoy", "Qalandary", "Gulyor-Shahnoz", "Bayot", "Dugohi", "Husayniy". "Chorgoh", "Miskin" and "Nasrullovi" series of songs and tunes took place. He recreated a number of Uzbek folk tunes and songs: "Subhidam", "Yol'giz", "Saiqal", "Figon", "Oraz", "Begi", "Sultan" and other

performing activities together with composition. . Yunus Rajabi made a great contribution to the formation of Uzbek musical drama.

Maqam in Arabic means place, rank, and the plural form of maqamot. In the past, the term maqam was used in different meanings in the sense of the place where the sounds that make up the tunes and songs are located in musical instruments, i.e. curtain. In order to build the system of twelve statuses, first of all, it was necessary to create perfect veils of fundamental novelty value (or to correctly define them on a scientific basis). This scientific task was assigned to musicologists.

Eastern scientists widely used numerical (mathematical) methods applied to science by ancient Greek theorists, including Pythagoras (approx. 580-520 BC) in the study of the problems of the science of music. After all, in order to create classical music systems that can be compared to luxurious architectural structures, first of all, it was required to have musical devices developed on the basis of exact measurements. In the subject of scientific analysis, the compositional bases of the melody - the smallest unit is the nagma (musical sound, tone), as well as the gender based on the ratios of two nagma (interval) and its additions (mainly, four-five-step tetra -pentachords) and issues such as formation of groups (octave-scale sound series) consisting of the combination of genders were applied. In this case, the straight line (1) assumed as the string of the oud instrument is divided into two equal parts (1:2) zul-kull (pure octave). The scholars of the East - Abu Nasir Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Mansur Ibn Zayla and Alisher Nawai, made a great contribution to music, and his followers, on the contrary, conducted research on the theoretical development of perfect pitch lines. Such theoretical situations are in accordance with the artistic and aesthetic requirements of that time, including the initial interpretation given to this style based on the new style that began to gain priority in music: the new style is a general set of melodies A musical process in which the principle of rising towards the climax (peak) takes a leading place in the wave-like movement.

Naturally, the composition of the new style, which is being formed in the Movarounnahr region, includes local musical traditions, which have priority from the point of view of ideology. According to musicologist A. Muhambetova, musical samples called tunes were the pre-Islamic culture of the Turkic peoples.

The system of twelve statuses was scientifically classified for the first time by Safiuddin Urmavi (approx. 1230-1294), a great scientist and musician who lived in the thirteenth century. The summary of this scientific process is as follows: the great classifier divided the main rocks that made up the composition of the aggregates into two groups - 7 four-step (in the form of a pentachord) high class rocks, and their (lower and upper student samples) as a result of mutual

integration (joining) with each other, managed to create (7x12)84 totals from bottom to top. But most of these theoretically developed ensembles were separated separately for musical practice.

In this case, the composition of sufficient harmonious (consonance) intervals in the composition of two factors-sounds is firstly made up of pure octaves (zul-kull), then pure kivinta (zul-khams) and pure fourths (zul-arba'). reached The method of expressing these intervals using numbers, formed by dividing the oud string into two (1:2), three (2:3) and four (3:4), was used in the ancient East (Egypt, China, Babylon, etc.).) scientists know well. Pythagoras, who creatively mastered these scientific traditions, in turn developed his famous tetraktyd as an expression of the numbers (1:2;2:3;3:4) of these intervals. (Turkish, Iranian, Arabic, Tajik, etc.) It seems that the melodies of the old traditional tunes are classified in the form of phonetic structures. For example, among them there are names such as Navrozi Arab, Navrozi Bayoti, Navrozi Khoro, Navrozi Ajam, which mean certain sayings performed on the days of the Navroz holiday, which has been widely celebrated since the long past, and later, In connection with the status system classification, the name of this holiday was attributed to each of them. The reason for this assumption is that the composition of the subsidiaries is not the same.

The maqamot system is a complex of Bukhara Shashmaqami, Khorezim maqams and Ferghana-Tashkent maqam roads, which arose as a result of the development of the classical traditions of maqamatism on a national musical basis. In this case, Bukhara and Khorezim maqams appear in the form of the Shashmaqom system, and in contrast to them, the Fergana - Tashkent maqam roads appear in the form of a scattered system.

The classical music of the Uzbek-Tajik peoples - Shashmaqom was expressed in Bukhara in the middle of the seventeenth century by court professional musicians and musicologists in the form of a majestic series consisting of six maqams. These maqams are named as follows:

1. Buzruk is big, big, great.
2. True, true, real.
3. Navo - meaning-melody, sad melody, love melody.
4. Dugoh - two places, two places, two curtains.
5. Segoh - three places, three places, three curtains.
6. Iraq is attributed to the name of a well-known Arab country.

It is worth noting that Shashmaqom means the best. Because each of these curtain associations has harmonious (gentle) parts

These curtains, whose general index (9) is more than the main sound - the number of notes in them (8), gained priority in the creative process:

Tasnif and Tarji tunes. It was said that each status in the system of six statuses consists of two major sections - instrumental and vocal. According to the Bukhara tradition, the instrumental music section of maqams is called Mushkilot. This term comes in the meaning of difficulties, including the fact that the main theme of the statuses is tested by circle methods of different complexity and thus develops at the level of a separate part and category. The problem section consists of five components, which are named as follows:

1. Classified, created perfect work.
2. Over and over again, repetitive.
3. Cervical-palatal flange part.
4. Muhammas-five, five.
5. Baldness is heavy.

It should be said that although the names of maqam instrumental tunes have various meanings, almost all of them mean circular methods in the text of maqam. Therefore, when Gardun, Mukhammas or Sakil are called, first of all, certain circle methods are meant. The Mushkilot instrumental sections of the maqams begin with tunes called Tasnif.

As the system of meanings of maqam acquires a different color in each maqam, it is first expressed in the structure of the initial melody of the classification part of the maqam. Usually, the theme of this melody is presented in a small but relatively complete form. After all, in the form of status themes, incomparable examples of the concept of a musical theme in general come to life, in which the mental states of hearts suffering from great pain of love are as if imprinted in songs. In fact, this category of musical themes begins to show its spiritual (spiritual) influence and scope during the skilled performances of the musicians (and the songs of the hafiz).

In their treatises, Abu Nasr Farabi and Ibn Sina commented on the theory of Eastern music, especially the theoretical basis of status issues, and in their works, this issue found its classical definition. The consistent teaching of the great scientists about status clarified the content of the works of music theorists who lived and created in the 13th-15th centuries. This situation is clearly visible in the works of Urmawi, Shirozi, Husayni and Jami. Al-Khorazmi. In the history of musical culture of the 9th-10th centuries, the great lexicographer Abu Abdullah Muhammad Ibn Yusuf al-Katib al-Khorazmi from Central Asia

Mafotikhul-ulum (the key to knowledge) also has a special place in the section devoted to music. This work of Khorezimi is one of the important sources for illuminating the history of science and culture of the peoples of Central Asia. In particular, the musical instruments of that time are fully described in the part of this dictionary about music, and detailed information is given about each of them.

In general, Eastern scientists considered music to be one of the sciences of philosophy, and therefore included it in their books written in the style of a dictionary. In this, they undoubtedly took into account the artistic-aesthetic power and social-educational role of music. Music science was in it as one of the mathematical sciences. The reason for this is that the sounds that make up the music are in a certain proportion to each other and are explained by some mathematical rules. Initially, the pitch of the sounds that make up the intervals was measured by the length of the string. In this case, narrow parts are determined by geometry, and different intervals are extracted from its known parts. For example, the two-to-one ratio (that is, the sound produced by half of the open string in relation to itself) is an interval of the octave level and is expressed in mathematics as 2:1 (status 1).

Shashmaqom is basically a group of statuses that have a high place in the musical heritage of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples of Central Asia: there are classical tunes and songs that are interconnected by tools such as pitch, tone, method, form, and style.

Position directions:

Yalla (yallas based on the genre of authority).

Big song.

Bukhara "Shashmaqomi".

Status of Khorezm.

Fergana-Tashkent status roads.

Uzbek national status art center.

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